

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

Corpus of session reports v2

WP5_D5.2 Version 1.1

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Copyright This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727066

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H2020-SC6-REV-INEQUAL-2016

Grant Agreement number: 727066

1st November 2016 – 31st October 2019

Corpus of session reports

WP5_D5.2*

Deliverable description			
Filename	WYRED_WP5_D5.2_version_1.1.pdf		
Type	Report		
Dissemination level	PU		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.3607553		
Due Date (in months)	M25		
Deliverable contributors			
Version No.	Name, Institution	Role	Last update
1	Early Years – the organisation for young children Northern Ireland	WP5 Leader	30/11/2018
1.1	WYRED Consortium		14/01/2020

* cfr. GA – Annex I Part A – 1.3.2 WT2 – list of deliverables

Table of Contents

1	Introduction to the WYRED Project	3
1.1	WYRED mission	3
1.2	Work Package 5 (WP5) in context	4
2	Social Dialogue Phase	6
2.1	Objectives	6
2.2	WP5 Social Dialogues Cycle 2	7
3	List of tables	8
3.1	Completed dialogues by partner and numbers of participants	8
3.2	Range of evidence gathering tools used in the sessions	9
4	Description of the activities	9
4.1	Face to face Dialogues	9
4.2	Online Dialogues	10
4.3	Online Usage Tables	12
5	Partner Reports	15
5.1	What went well within the dialogues (Feedback from partner reports)	15
5.2	Main insights relating to Dialogue Outcomes - coming from Partner Reports CYCLE 2	17
5.3	Interpretation – coming from Partner Reports	25
6	Recommendations from facilitating the dialogues	32
7	Conclusions	33
8	Appendices	35
8.1	WP5 Updated Social Dialogues Report Template	35
8.2	WP5 Corpus of Session Reports by Partner	35
9	References	35

1 Introduction to the WYRED Project

This document collects the findings from the WP5 Social Dialogues package carried out between July 2017 to September 2018. The process involved examination and analysis of the partners documentation around the Social Dialogues in Cycle 2. This document constitutes the second WP5 deliverable of the project, the first submitted in June 2017. Potential improvements are suggested in a list of recommendations at the end of the document.

The WYRED project (netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society) (García-Peñalvo, 2016b, 2017, 2018; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016; Griffiths et al., 2017) provides a framework for research in which children and young people can express and explore their perspectives and interests in relation to digital society, and also a platform (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2018; García-Peñalvo, 2016a; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018) from which they can communicate their perspectives to other stakeholders effectively through innovative engagement processes. WYRED is implementing a generative research cycle (WYRED Consortium, 2017a, 2017b) involving networking, dialogue, participatory research and interpretation phases centred around and driven by children and young people. From this a diverse range of outputs, critical perspectives and other insights are emerging to inform policy and decision-making in relation to children and young people's needs in relation to digital society.

1.1 WYRED mission

Before the Brexit referendum in the UK, there was a campaign to give a vote to young people over 14 the vote, since it was their lives that would be affected in the future by the outcome. It didn't succeed, and campaigns of this kind rarely do. While society sometimes listens, through youth debates and panels, it rarely acts on young people's perspectives or initiatives. The figures show that young people in Europe don't feel involved in society. Youth voices are marginal, and don't reach decision-makers. The WYRED project aims to change this, amplifying youth voices, and connecting them to decision-makers.

This might have been appropriate in times when change was slow, but as society goes digital, the speed of change is increasing, and society struggles to understand and adapt to the pace of change (for example "fake news"), the different perspectives of the young on the digital aspects

of our lives are invaluable in helping society to adapt and prepare for the future in which they will live. WYRED aims to surface these digital perspectives, helping us all to understand the change.

Young people's opinions are frequently seen (or characterised) as simply individual views, and therefore not representative. There is a need to show evidence for their perspectives if they are to have an influence. The WYRED project aims to help young people research the digital issues that matter to them, so that their concerns are backed up with evidence, so that they can have an influence.

WYRED aims to:

- Amplify youth voices.
- Strengthen youth views through youth-led research.
- Connect youth with decision-makers.
- Broaden understanding of the digital society.
- Make youth perspectives matter.

1.2 Work Package 5 (WP5) in context

These work packages WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP7 make up the WYRED cycle. The decision was taken to start the second WYRED cycle earlier than originally planned in autumn 2017, in order to adjust the cycle to the rhythms of the target groups involved. This means that for some time, the first and second cycles were running in parallel. This is not considered to be an issue, particularly when it is taken into consideration that as the project moves forward the WYRED cycle is increasingly expected to become a continuous cycle in which different groups may be in different stages of the cycle at the same time. However, though the flexibility it has afforded has allowed the partners to adapt better to their local contexts, some issues around international participation continues to be a challenge and still needs addressed collectively by all the partners.

The full cycle of activity in WYRED starts with network building in WP 4, in which the children and young people (C&YP) who will participate in the research cycle are attracted and engaged and the principal themes that represent their concerns are identified. The next work package (5) focuses on social dialogue around those themes, exploring them in order to identify key research questions relating to the digital society that concern children and young people. In the

subsequent work package (6), these children and young people, supported by the partners, focus on designing and implementing research activities to explore these questions and issues in a range of different ways. WP7 focuses on the interpretation and evaluation both of the process and its resulting production types by the young research participants and partners, and of different formats and artefacts that will be used to present the results, principally insights and recommendations to different target groups at policy level and in wider society. The final phase of the cycle in WP8 focuses on the dissemination and exploitation of these results, though this work package runs throughout the project, engaging in the valorization of the WYRED activity through workshops, event participation, online activity and association. These 5 work packages form a cycle that is aimed at generating insights relating to the perspectives and concerns of children and young people in relation to digital society.

Figure 1: WYRED work packages (WP)

The present report focusses on WP5 and presents the activities of the Social Dialogues Phase.

2 Social Dialogue Phase

2.1 Objectives

A key aim of WYRED is engaging young people in a process of social dialogue that gives them a voice and help them use this process to design participatory research projects that allow them to surface and explore their concerns about the digital society in ways defined by them.

After the first network building stage of the WYRED cycle, the focus passed to social dialogue: WP5 – Facilitate a set of dialogues to explore the themes in WP4 (brought out through Delphi questionnaire) to generate an open set of appropriate questions / key research questions relating to the digital society that concern children and young people which will then be investigated and researched (in as many ways as possible) in WP6.

In a project such as WYRED, which involves a large number of participants from diverse contexts designing their own research-focused activities, many of whom will be from non-academic backgrounds, it is very important to ensure that the work is based on rich questions that are relevant to children and young people. It is also important to ground the research in the realities of the digital society in Europe as experienced by children and young people.

The aim of this work package facilitates a set of dialogues that explore the themes identified in the previous work package (WP4). The transcripts and recordings of the dialogue sessions are analysed using a range of techniques including thematic coding, corpus analysis, and other analytics processes. The results of this process are used in online discussions by —core groupsll in each country, made up of a selection of the dialogue participants and the partners, in order to generate an open set of appropriate questions that will then be investigated in the activities that take place in WP6.

The dialogues allow the participants in the process to express their views, speak of their experience and identify the aspects that they would like to explore further. In order to ensure a sufficient range of arenas for dialogue this work takes place both online and off-line in workshops organised by the partners.

2.2 WP5 Social Dialogues Cycle 2

The social dialogues continue to function well into Cycle 2, a wide diversity of participants have engaged in these processes over the course of the project so far and valuable perspectives have been shared. Reflection over the second year has pointed to the fact that it is unfortunate that the outputs of the dialogues only feed the next stage of the cycle and are not more widely shared since they have a value in themselves. For this reason, the WYRED Insights document presented as part of WP7, will draw on the results of the dialogues as well as the outputs of the projects.

There is a strong perception among the partners of the value of the dialogues, not only as a stage in the cycle that makes the rest possible - the discussions provide the momentum and the ideas to move forward into the research phase - but also as intrinsically valuable in themselves. They constitute a valuable opportunity to engage children and young people in analysing, reflecting and critically thinking about their own generation in terms of what they identify as their principal concerns and problems in relation to the digital society. The result of the process is frequently that the children and young people involved derive a sense of empowerment through sharing their knowledge and perspectives, and furthermore that the issues that concern them are also relevant for their peers and for society. For many the discussions also involved exploration of core values and views of the future. Going forward, there will be a slight change in the dialogues, which is in fact already taking place. As the EU review report points out there is a need for greater focus in the themes WYRED covers, and there is therefore a commitment to the use of a set of themes relating to the digital society. It is expected that though this may limit that freedom for the conversation to range, it will lead to greater potential for impact.

In relation to this, the reporting of the dialogues remains an issue. Though it is perhaps understandable that as the dialogue sessions are often now the first contact with WYRED, and therefore facilitators feel the need for a light touch, there is a need for greater homogeneity in the reporting. Though the template created is very clear and easy to use, work needs to be done to provide a greater degree of detail in some reports since this is vital for the extraction of useful insights from the dialogues. Partners need to commit to more detailed reporting of the dialogues. Another issue is the need for more online events to take place in the project, and efforts should be made to ensure some of these are online dialogues.

3 List of tables

3.1 Completed dialogues by partner and numbers of participants

CYCLE 1 and 2 - Face to Face Social Dialogues

Partner	Total Dialogues Stand alone	Total Dialogues Same group	Total participants	Age groups	Dates	Duration
CYCLE 1						
Boundaries		2	16	14-15	June 17	2 hrs
DOGA	2 + 2		45 + 49	15-19 & 20-24	May – June 17 July 17 – April 18	+2 hours
Early Years	3		46	10-11, 11-14	May 17 – June 17	1.5/2hrs
Moves		4	63	15 -22	April 17 – March 18	Under 2 hours
Oxfam		6	14	15 and 23-26	May 17 – April 18	Every 2 weeks +2 hours
PYE	2		17	13 - 20	June 17	+ 2 hours
TAU	4		62	16	May 17	1.5/2hrs
USAL	3	1	150	15-19	Feb 17 – April17 May17 – June17	
YEU	3		48	15-19,20-24,25-29	June 17	2 hours
TOTALS CYCLE 1	17 + 2	13	461 + 49			
Partner CYCLE 2	Total Dialogues Stand alone	Total Dialogues Same group	Total participants	Age groups	Dates	Duration
Boundaries	3	5	99	10 -14 17-18	April 18 – Oct 2018	1-3 hours
DOGA	2		10	15-19	May 18	+2 hours
Early Years		4	48	10-11	March 18 – June 18	1 a week +2 hours
Moves		1	26	17 - 18	April 18 – June 18	2 hours
Oxfam		4	11	22-24	Nov 17 – Jan 18	Every 2 weeks + 2 hours
PYE	10		30	13-20	Nov 17 – Dec 17	+2 hrs
TAU		26	49	16-18	July 18 – Aug 18	1 a week 1.5 – 2 hrs
USAL	12		75	15-19	Dec 17	+2 hours
YEU	9		190	10-14,15-19,20-24,25-29	March18 & July18-August18	+ 2 hours

TOTALS	36	40	538			
CYCLE 2						

3.2 Range of evidence gathering tools used in the sessions

Checklist for Dialogues - completed by partners	CYCLE 1	CYCLE 2
Attendance sheet for each Dialogue session	x	x
Consent forms signed from C&YP and parents (if necessary) for participation and use of images	x	x
Did you take photographs?	x	x
Other evidence gathering tool used?	Video	Video Recordings

4 Description of the activities

4.1 Face to face Dialogues

The Social Dialogues handbook (Appendix 1) continues in this cycle to provide guidance for the partners to follow during the Social Dialogue phase and assistance in addressing the identified issues and concerns that could arise, using a range of techniques, when facilitating dialogues with children and young people such as:

- Ability to facilitate groups face to face
- Ability to facilitate groups on line
- Facilitate interactive gatherings
- Awareness of facilitation techniques to promote active involvement
- Tools of engagement
- Supporting articulation of issues of concern

- Relationship building
- Understanding the technology
- Equal regard – diversity of perspectives
- Low participation of C&YP and other stakeholders
- Lack of understanding
- Low degree of interaction
- Not seen as relevant or interesting

The dialogues' primary focus was to give a wide range of children and young people the opportunity to share their voices around a range of topics and themes in relation to the digital society that interest or concern them.

The Dialogues continue to provide a forum for engendered lively and energetic debate among young people – the themes presented by the facilitators were based on the Delphi questionnaire topics (see Delphi Report). The partners identified possible research questions/areas of foci under the prioritized themes.

(See D54 Key Research Questions – list of suggestions for the research activities arising from the Dialogues)

4.2 Online Dialogues

Aims of the online dialogues

- To promote engaging conversations around the subjects that have been identified as important in the Delphi process.
- To consolidate young people's engagement with WYRED.
- To identify key questions for exploration that derive from the discussion around these themes.
- For some, opportunities for language practice.

Though the dynamics of online interaction are different to face to face (F2F), many principles remain similar: there is a need to create a safe space for interaction hence the online platform,

where all views are respected. There is a need for “rich” questions that open up the conversation and move it forward, a need to encourage and then recognise participation by all, and the capacity to be still and listen when the conversation has developed its own life.

The local focus of the dialogues has been to some extent at the expense of the international dimension in WYRED. There have been challenges in achieving continuous interaction in the platform, and partners have identified the need to organise a schedule of online events and specific collaborative work between WYRED groups from different countries. This is currently under way. It is expected to contribute to the wider impact of the project and to the value gatekeepers and children and young people ascribe to the project.

The WYRED platform is a safe space for children and children and young people to engage with each other within the project. The option of using existing social media, such as Instagram or others, despite their familiarity and convenience for young people, had to be ruled out because their business models are based on the notion of personal data as a saleable commodity. Therefore, none of them comply with the ethical foundations of WYRED. Although the sensible decision was taken not to develop from scratch, the complexity of the emerging WYRED approach and the requirements involved caused delays. The platform functions appropriately and complies with all the ethical requirements of the project. It is however a less dynamic and less attractive instrument than most children and young people are used to, and this affects its use, particularly as a continuous communication tool. Specific organised events and collaborations do however work and the focus in the final year of the project will be on using it in this way.

The development of the WYRED Platform and the lack of experience of the members of the consortium on moderating/facilitating on line dialogues has been addressed with a forward plan for the online dialogues. During the project meeting in Bath, an online facilitation training was defined as one of the tasks to carry out.

The online training for Facilitators is now organized in three webinars of 90 minutes that will take place during the week of 12, 13 November 2018 and 13 December 2018. The following diagram provides an overview of the topics covered in each webinar. The trainers will be: Alicia García-Holgado from GRIAL - USAL (1st webinar), Igor Jojkic from YEU (2nd webinar) and Federica Cicala from Oxfam (3rd webinar).

Meet.google.com will be used as the webinar tool, to create the meeting rooms and to share the links for each webinar. Moreover, sessions will be recorded so that the partners and facilitators who cannot attend the live sessions can access the materials. All the information about the training and the support afterwards will be through a private community in the WYRED Platform. All facilitators in the WYRED Platform are members of this community.

Info graphic below outlines the webinar themes across the 3 sessions:

It is hoped that after the Webinars that all partners will be in a better position to facilitate and involve children and young people in engaging and maintaining online conversations through the platform. And to this end an Online Festival is organised from January 2019.

4.3 Online Usage Tables

Despite the challenges with continuous interaction on the platform between children and Young people from all the partner countries, C&YP have however been using the platform on a local level. Fig 1 depicts usage by age profile on the platform. Fig 2. Depicts usage on the platform by gender.

Online usage 2017- Fig. 1

Total users under 30 years old: 419

Online Usage by gender 2017-Fig 2.

Users under 30 years old: 419

Fig. 3 reflects the usage on the Platform. As depicted below a total of 67 different users across all countries have created threads on the online forum. As depicted other countries are represented outside the partner countries due to the fact that some Partners e.g. (YEU) are an international based organisation and other young people were engaged on the online dialogues?

Platform Usage-Fig. 3

- 67 different users have created forum threads
- 172 different users have participated in the forums

Forum Threads Fig. 4

Fig. 4 show the number of forum threads created along the last year (the first statistics are from 11/11/2017) until 22/10/2018. Regarding active threads (red line) reflects the activity in the forums, it shows the forum threads that have at least two interactions (comments) in the last months. From the graph we can see that the active forum threads are a lot lower than the forum threads and that active activity has plateaued. Going forward the work with the webinars with the

partners in increasing facilitation knowledge and capacity and the plans for the online dialogues should show an increase in Cycle 3 in relation to online forum thread activity.

5 Partner Reports

5.1 What went well within the dialogues (Feedback from partner reports)

76 Social dialogue sessions took place from July 2017 to September 2018 across the 9 partners with a wide range of nationalities taking part. **538** Children and Young People (C&YP) took part during the Social Dialogue phase.

For the WP5 Social Dialogues, Partners were instructed to follow the prompts given to help gather and collate the relevant information from the Dialogues

The Dialogues are a safe space for discussion - C&YP can talk about what they want. Although facilitators during this Cycle 2 phase need to introduce the topics that relate to the WYRED and Delphi themes around the Digital Society.

Children's voices need to be heard so that their messages will be brought to decision makers. The Dialogues need to capture the RICH conversations the C&YP have as much as possible.

- What happened during the sessions?
- What did you achieve?
- Focus on impact and content of the dialogues.

Partners were reminded about the Role of the Facilitator:

- To interpret and draw out the significant information
- To be proactive and extract information from the discussions.
- To focus/drive conversations to digital society using the themes arising from the Delphi. (Refer to list of WYRED Themes)
- To help C&YP to reflect and focus the conversation in order to make conclusions and recommendations later on.

- To collect and record specific information from the dialogues:

- What do the C&YP know?

- What don't they know?

- What do they need to find out?

Partners were reminded to use the WP5 Guidelines handbook for reference and ideas

Partners were required to complete the updated WP5 template Fig. 4 below to cover the substance from the social dialogues

Fig. 4

CYCLE 2	WP5 Social Dialogues qualitative data
Number of themes discussed	
Titles of themes discussed	
Themes discussed related to Delphi results	
<p>Main insights relating to Dialogue Outcomes.</p> <p>Report on most relevant and significant aspects of the sesión or sessions.</p>	
<p>Record objectively what the C&YP said during the sessions.</p> <p>A description of the conversation - possibly use a voice/video recorder during the dialogue and then the Facilitator can summarise and record here the main content of the dialogue/s</p>	
Interpretation -	

<p>What surprised you the most about what the C&YP said?</p> <p>What was predictable?</p> <p>What was interesting?</p> <p>What was important?</p> <p>How this conversation relates to the Delphi and WYRED themes?</p>	
<p>Research Questions coming from this/these dialogue(s)</p>	

5.2 Main insights relating to Dialogue Outcomes - coming from Partner Reports CYCLE 2

YEU

- In the young people’s case, 3 groups worked in a set like a dialogue and 1 as a “question wall” and debriefing based on the topics covered. That helped participants to understand the process, be the centre of the discussion and debate each other’s opinions and be more productive. Therefore, there are a lot of opinions and notes collected.

- One group was made by European Participants that made it easy to have diversity of opinions, questions and topics covered. However, the other 3 groups Italian participants it was a bit difficult to have a deep discussion as there was a language gap.

- In the case of children as YEU isn’t used to working with this age group, it was a bit difficult to run the dialogue, so it ended up tackling online behavior, technology and actions that should be aware. As the session moved on there were no questions at that point addressed by the children.

USAL

- As regards different aspects of the “digital life”, in general YP claim information, awareness, prevention and training. This work should be aimed at all age groups since the globalization of the internet is conditioning that all people, from children to the elderly.
- Artificial intelligence is a fact. Machines capable of interacting with humans but without their own thoughts or a freely developed personality. Emotional education and knowledge of ourselves make the difference between us and the machines.

TAU

Instructor's insights:

- Choosing only one issue to deal with was difficult at the beginning, so we found a way to help the students: We asked them to watch pictures from their field trips and to think about possible solutions; then, they used stickers to emphasize their favorite issues. From this list, they picked one issue which is most important to them. This process helped them to focus on the mission.
- The method of producing a "futures wheel", alongside the session in which the students wrote down a brief for their campaign, helped them to conduct a focused group discussion, using the right terminology, to express their ideas.
- Based on the above, one generalization we can make is that a well-structured process helps the students to define the problems and the relative importance of different factors (institutional, cultural, etc.), which affect their ability to act. The “futures wheel” as a framework provides a workable framework and guideline.

Students' insights:

- The role of technology: There were disagreements about the need to relate to technology when discussing the future of society.
- The young students believed that they should be an example of peaceful coexistence between different religions and cultures: Arabs and Jews, religious and secular, who

succeeded in bridging the gaps and disagreements – studying and living together – wanted to express the idea that there is another way. Therefore, they argued that people should meet each other (online and offline) and share their common hobbies and interests to be more tolerant of other people from different cultures. As a result, three groups of students chose to deal with various aspects of social and economic gaps.

- Using their experience of living and working in the digital world, the students claim that social networks are catalysts for hate speech but can also be a promoter for social change. Therefore, several groups have finally decided to use technological tools to promote their solution.
- Using the “futures wheel” results, the student concluded that robots would do the routine works and therefore there will be not enough jobs for migrants, who have inappropriate skills. Therefore, the children of refugees should have the same education as Israelis, otherwise they will be pushed into a life of poverty and even crime. Following these observations, one group chose to deal with the issue of education for refugee children.
- The students argued that sustainability is an important goal; youngsters, leaders and public-opinion shapers should be convinced about the need to promote it. Therefore, one group chose to create a campaign that would promote sustainability.

PYE

- The young people were enthusiastic, passionate and engaged throughout. They offered some sensitive reflections and had first-hand experience to bear on the issues. There was trust, respect and humour throughout. One of the young people left saying ‘These are f*!%ing great talks’
- Participation in conversation was good. Engaged in topics. Listened to each other and the teachers. Video provided some starting points for conversation. Ice breaker game ‘All change if...’ was good to activate the group. Opened up discussion to include other topics than digital world and use of social media as prompted by video in previous

session. Working in small groups allowed quieter voices to be heard. Strong opinions on school uniform and able to reflect about pros and cons.

- Learning: The young people do have opinions and interest in online behaviours. There is more to be learnt about the negative impacts of cyber bullying. They were unwilling to have their photograph taken. The young people do have interest in online behaviours. There can be some sensitivity if some people are affected by the issues being discussed. E.g. a perpetrator of using false profiles in a harmful way.
- Learning: The sessions needs to be structured with engaging activities, clear and simple tasks and less whole group discussions. Some of the dominant voices can make it difficult for all the participants to express themselves. Small groups with adult supervision work best.

OXFAM

- Among the controversial issues identified in the first session participants decided to discuss about globalisation, as it is considered a transversal issue that impacts on several others.
- GLOBALISATION is perceived by the group as:
- An extension of borders which narrows distances and provides opportunities for new relationships becoming citizens of the world, but in the same time it fosters migrations which causes racism and integration issues
- It is a social phenomenon that promotes an exchange among cultures. Young people today don't feel connected with their local community, because through social media they can interact at a different level, causing a lack of attachment and participation in their neighbourhoods. They recognise that this means that they are losing their cultural bonds and that this trend impact at youth level in two ways: either rejecting globalisation embracing nationalistic movements, which are led by "ignorance" and "differences in thinking and seeing the world", or in homologation, same music, same shops, same fashion styles anywhere.
- Homologation led the discussion towards multinationals, marketing and the Economic VS political approach of globalisation. We agreed that globalisation is mainly a transformation of the economic system which started back in the nineties exporting

the capitalistic economic model in other regions of the world, but a real political commitment was never established to regulate the system causing poverty and inequalities within and among countries. In the same time local communities started to self-organise developing KM 0 agricultural productions and deliveries to contrast the side effects of agro-industrial productions.

- In the remaining time the group decided to discuss about “Self-representation” and the insights were quite interesting: in general, the group shared that self-representation is connected with how you project yourself on social media, where you have to show the best of your life and all the successes, because everyone look at what you share without going deeper conditioning the feelings and thoughts you can expose to the others and creating homologation in the type of experiences young people represent.
- In the same time, self-representation is seen as an opportunity to express yourself through blogs and social media, causing sometimes disinformation on relevant issues. It is difficult to distinguish between real and virtual life.
- Young people admit that they have fear and difficulties in exposing themselves in person taking the challenge of sharing fragilities and every day difficulties, because it costs efforts and also because they are conditioned by social models. People / “social media friends” have a judging attitude towards the others. For this reason, some of the group shred that usually they try to be assertive with other people moving their ideas in background. The person who shared this approach read a quotation: the talent of a person is visible only when he/she stop showing him/herself.
- Afterwards the discussion continued more informally, young people shared how they use social media in order to approach and make new friends and new partners. There is a specific “social code” to pick up partners: you might see in faculty or in a bar someone you physically like, therefore you find out the name and then you become friend in this person on Instagram / Facebook, once you are accepted as friend you put a like in the last post shared and you start following the profile page. If the other person does the same and keep liking your posts for at least a week, you can approach him/her in chat in order to combine an appointment. But it seems that, as share before, most of the time people project a totally different personality on social media, therefore in

many cases at the first appointment the prevalent feeling is disappointment towards the idea they made up of the other person.

MOVES

- Their intense form of self-organisation and how motivated they were in finding their themes.

EARLY YEARS

- We considered behaviour on the internet and began to formulate ideas of what is needed to be a safe, secure and moral digital citizen.
- Children highlighted issues of risk, safety and responsibility surrounding the use of ICT.
- We discussed how relationships affect everything we do in our lives and that relationship skills have to be learnt and practised.

DOGA

- The fifth social dialogue was arranged as an national social dialogue in Ataşehir, Istanbul with the participation of 10 students from Turkey.
- The topics from the Delphi questionnaires were distributed to the groups. Students found the topics interesting and expressed their eagerness to take part in WYRED

BOUNDARIES

- The most insightful part of the sessions actually related to the insights the children had relating to their digital lives, or lack of them. These were home schooled children whose parents felt strongly that school was not appropriate for them and in many cases the attitude to digital activity was similar. At most they used it for an hour a day for digital searches related to homework. Few however seemed to miss it, few knew others who used it much more. The only exception was two of the boys in the group who used gaming platforms, a lot. They had little interest in social media. The extent to which this was all due to parental decisions or their own was not entirely clear. It would be interesting to explore this further and this may take place in Cycle 3.

- The most relevant aspect of these sessions was how the participants took to the activity. They started the discussion before the presentation had finished and the first and second sessions worked well in a plenary format that they were actually unwilling to give up for the third session when they worked in groups. Much of the conversation was around living online and social media, and the same sense of the degree of complication involved emerged as had at Hayesfield. Poles emerged between those who were radically permissive and believed in their own freedom to manage their use, and those who felt some kind of control was needed. An interesting side note for plenaries is that one girl was deaf and gave me the microphone she had connected to her hearing aid, so she could hear, this was passed round and functioned as a manager of turn taking, which was useful given the degree of enthusiasm.
- The enthusiasm surprised their teacher, these are young people who are less academically minded, and the school focused on performing arts and crafts. She said they can often be quite apathetic and disinterested, but in this case they were not.

Main Insights from Online Dialogues: Summary

Areas of interest and Discussion included:

1. Globalisation and extension of migration
2. How we use social media
3. Digital Life-Information should be aimed at all ages from children to the elderly
4. Self-representation online
5. Homologation -marketing, multinationals economic versus political in an online context.
6. Risk, responsibility, safety when using ICT and online world
7. Behaviour on the internet, being a good digital citizen
8. Social networks can be a catalyst for hate

9. Future digital world influenced by robots and this may impact greatest on work for migrants
10. We have more to learn on the negative impacts of cyberbullying
11. Parents view of digital lives as being inappropriate and how this manifested in children.
12. Poles emerged between those who were radically permissive and believed in their own freedom to manage their use of social media, and those who felt some kind of control was needed.

In relation to delivery and content partners said:

- A lot of opinions and notes collected over the SD phase
- Trust, respect and humour displayed in Social dialogues
- Working in small groups allowed the quieter voices to be heard
- A lot of interest and opinions in relation to online behaviours
- Children and young people were enthusiastic, passionate and engaged
- At times there were language and translation issues
- Sensitivity existed around some issues discussed
- A well-structured social dialogue phase helped children and young people define their issues
- C&YP agreed they needed to meet online and offline to share common interest and promote tolerance
 - C&YP who are less academically minded, and who focused on performing arts and crafts can often be quite apathetic and disinterested, but in this case they were not. (Teacher observation)
 - Some C&YP were very diffident about speaking at all, while others monopolised the conversation. It took time to establish a way of working together

5.3 Interpretation – coming from Partner Reports

What surprised you the most about what the C&YP said?

YEU

Cycle 2 The process really empowered the participants. Coming from different backgrounds and as youth workers they felt it is difficult to be heard or build alliances. They saw through this process a chance for them to engage and also said that they will take the tool back home to engage more people. At the same time, they got to see WYRED as a project that can engage them even more and get to affect rather than live within other people's decisions.

(This process should be a standard procedure to consultations in order to create or change policies. It is also a first way to involve young people and therefore engage them in processes that affect their futures.)

This was a chance to reflect on the fact of majorities and minorities and how the choices of many affect the final result. Based on the time and the diversity of the group (Italians, Spanish, Greeks, FYROM/Macedonians, Belgians and Turkish) the group got flipcharts (one per topic) and put down the most important points and got to observe them in a World Café methodology.

In this case, there was an issue of language, therefore participants got to discuss before they write and then they wrote similar points in their national language. Most points were rather problems that they were facing based on their opinion. (tradition, fake images created by media etc).

Having a diverse group and offering different languages, proved the diversity and inclusion that WYRED wants to achieve. The outcomes were not so different from the previous consultations but this type of session gave the real picture of diversity of WYRED and what does the project try to achieve.

In our opinion it's important to assure translations and inclusive solutions to be able to include the opinion of young people from diverse backgrounds or cultural differences.

USAL

What surprised you the most about what the C&YP said?

YP suggest involving also parents and adults in a training on a conscious and informed approach to the digital society challenges.

What was predictable?

The focus on the risks of the digital environment and negative effects on YP; a feeling of fear towards the future.

What was interesting?

The picture summarizes the weight of different values for YP from the external ones to the really important.

In general, YP are conscious and seriously concerned with their future.

They are **centered more on the individual** than on globality as the engine of change.

What was important?

To ask for support from experienced adults (educators, trainers, mentors...). To be open to reflection and training.

How this conversation relates to the Delphi and WYRED themes?

Mainly the topics are in line with the Delphi themes, considering that the YP had the possibility to know previously the questions of the Delphi survey and the first results of the data analysis.

TAU

It was surprising to find that some young students were reluctant to talk about the role of technology in the future society – they felt that it diverted the discussion into a dead end. However, most of them have changed their mind about it along the process. It was also surprising to find out that although some of them came from very conservative communities, they were not afraid to discuss gender and LGBT issues.

- It is important to mention that the participants were really inspired by the lecturers and the tours. Therefore, we believe that this is a useful means to give them the chance "to dive into the problem". Furthermore, they lacked information about ways to influence the key decision makers. Therefore, lectures about social media, information society, journalism and lobbying were very important to their sense of competence and helped them to use media tools more efficiently.
- It was interesting, yet predictable, that they were fed up with the traditional politics and "old" media.
- Many of the topics appeared in the Delphi survey. The tendency of most participants was to discuss the social perspective.
- It was interesting to see that work groups that were guided by a young junior instructor were very creative, and sometimes more dedicated to the project than those guided by a senior instructor. This may be an indication that we need to give the students more opportunities to lead the process - in accordance with the real WYRED spirit.

Out of the box thinking: The "feel of inventiveness" was everywhere

PYE

We spoke about the value of face to face interactions and dialogue between people from different countries. We would like to pursue the possibility of bi-lateral or multilateral exchange opportunities. As the relationship of trust develops with the young people and the organisation

the potential for more in-depth discussion and development of research questions will increase.

OXFAM

The overall sessions went well. Some of the participants were comfortable with non-formal settings, for others it was a new experience, but all of them actively contributed to the development of the session bringing their personal experiences and perspectives both on social issues and their lifestyles.

OIT included among the topics of discussion globalisation and the Agenda 2030 as most of the participants were not aware of this international legal framework. It was an important step to engage YP in the research phase and motivate them to further explore the issues presented into the social dialogues.

The second cycle has been smoother to deliver because the activities to undertake were more defined and young people had a clearer idea of what was expected from them.

Furthermore, the University of Roma Tre supported a lot the students recognising the value of their researches and providing the space to discuss them in a public event.

MOVES

Young people care for themselves, the others and the future.

EARLY YEARS

At the young ages of 9/10 years old all children are digitally literate and have accessed some form of social media despite age restrictions.

A lot of children have experienced hacking and cyberbullying

All the children are aware of online safety however many do not implement in practice in relation to their online activity.

Children were really engaged in discussions and fully participated giving rich discussions.

DOGA

For the fourth social dialogue we welcomed international students with a warming up activity aimed at strengthening their self-image. The activity was an arts exercise, using a dipping technique with acrylic colours. The students were divided into 4 groups of 7 students, according to the colours they selected. For sheets of poster paper of different colours were handed out to the groups, and each group chose their theme. First, the students discussed the main theme and listed and presented their problems to other groups. After the round of presentations, four main topics were given to the students, to work on in small groups: sustainable development, environment issues, social media and entrepreneurship.

Their respective teachers also attended the dialogue and shared their interest for the WYRED project.

The main activities carried out were creating a terrarium, marketing and keychain making using polyacrylate.

For the fifth social dialogue, we welcomed students from Turkey. The WYRED project was briefly introduced to the newcomers. After the introduction and a basic project presentation, research techniques and project aims were explained to the students. The Project platform was also shown to the students; in particular, students were shown the projects stored on the platform, so that they could review and score them.

All students made equal contributions to the activity. They found the topics interesting and expressed their eagerness to take part in WYRED.

BOUNDARIES

Their indifference to the digital world was interesting. It was not politic to explore too much whether this was due to parental attitudes, as this all take place during a period of initial contact, but it is an area that could be fascinating. Predictable, most of their initial attitudes to education, and to animal rights and gaming. This was an example of a context where the more interesting things had to be elicited and teased out. They had little culture of "discussion" so this had to be supported by a lot of questioning. The animal rights discussion became interesting when they started to see the possibility of a kind of digital activism. The potential work in education could prove to be very interesting, though the discussions were less so, apart from some hard moments spent talking about some experience of bullying. Both areas

outlined by the RQs are important, though neither fits very closely to Cycle 3 areas of focus. Though the children might be interested, the parents are resistant to a more focused exploration of digital themes.

There was a strong sense that young people don't have a voice, almost outrage, across the 3 groups (school culture?). The subject of Brexit was commented on quite a lot, many felt they should have had a vote on their own future. Predictable comments about experiences of adult misunderstandings of their online world, online safety (they know this), environmental and educational concerns. Interesting was the number of nuanced comments about social media, and other issues such as gender and self-image. The sense that it is complicated and that the endless focus on safety is generally unsophisticated. Also some comments on the lines of we know the problem, and we deal with it , but we need more tools and ideas for "how best to deal with it".

Important was the sense that there could be valuable ideas coming out of these groups, that their understandings are not likely to be the black and white we might want, but richer for that. Hoping to re-engage in Cycle 3.

The complexity of their view and their awareness of the nuances was surprising, they were more sophisticated than they are often given credit for, and ambiguous, simultaneously aware of their roles as consumers, and critical of them. Predictable some of the complaints about simplistic adult views of their lives and decisions.

It was all interesting, some of the key aspects are covered above. What was important was just how interested they were, and how willing to participate. It was a valuable demonstration of how WYRED can work. The fact that the school culture is more geared to project work may help, but the reactions of the teacher indicate that the autonomy given was positive too.

The relation to WYRED themes was good, and more so since almost all of this fits into Cycle 3 themes.

What surprised you most about what the C&YP said? Summary:

- Young people care for themselves, others and the future.

- Social Dialogues are a useful tool to engage C&YP and many said they would take it back home and use it to engage more with others.
- Word café methodology worked really well.
- Having a diverse group with different languages proved diversity and what WYRED wants to achieve. We need to assure translation to make sure this works well.
- Young people suggested involving parents in training to inform them on digital society.
- C&YP really found the topics interesting
- Some young people were reluctant to talk about role of technology in future society.
- Although some young people came from very conservative societies, they openly discussed gender and LGBT issues. Young people are fed up with traditional politics.
- Many topics discussed appeared in the DELPHI.
- Students leading the process worked well, very creative.
- A lot of trust built between facilitator and C&YP
- Young people recognized the value of their research.
- Really empowered C&YP.
- At the young ages of 9/10 yrs old all children are digitally literate and have accessed some form of social media despite age restrictions.
- A lot of children have experienced hacking and cyberbullying
- All the children are aware of online safety however many do not implement in practice in relation to their online activity.
- Children were really engaged in discussions and fully participated giving rich discussions.
- C&YP had little culture of “discussion” so this had to be supported by a lot of questioning.
- Though the children might be interested, the parents are resistant to a more

- focused exploration of digital themes
- There was a strong sense that young people don't have a voice, almost outrage,
- across the 3 groups
- Also, some comments on the lines of we know the problem, and we deal with it.
- but we need more tools and ideas for "how best to deal with it".
- The complexity of their view and their awareness of the nuances was surprising,
- they were more sophisticated than they are often given credit for, and ambiguous,
- simultaneously aware of their roles as consumers, and critical of them.

6 Recommendations from facilitating the dialogues

At the moment our experience with face to face dialogues seems good and each partner has organized and reported the results of these activities. The next step is to see how to organize online sessions, so to document also at distance synchronous and a-synchronous interaction with the young participants. So the main recommendations reflect what needs to be done in relation to the online dialogues.

- The partners will be trained in the online facilitation interaction methodology. – organised for November 2018.
- the need to organise a schedule of online events and specific collaborative work between WYRED groups from different countries. This is currently under way. It is expected to contribute to the wider impact of the project and to the value gatekeepers and children and young people ascribe to the project.
- Activity on the platform needs to be engaging for C&YP to take part in.
- Embrace all the ideas by the C&YP as long as a connection can be made to the online world.
- All project ideas need to clearly link to the DELPHI / WYRED themes otherwise we will not be able to collect information at a higher level to aggregated results.

- Partners need to commit to using the platform as a key element and help users engage.
- A wide range of online events need to be scheduled in the platform.
- Projects/Online dialogues need to be themed in platform as to protect younger users e.g. some of the #Me Too content not appropriate for 10yr olds.
- Online Dialogues for under 14 years was problematic due to registration issues with email addresses on getting registered with the platform – other registration avenues to be explored.
- Adequate time needs to be given for fruitful dialogues to happen.
- Keep a balance between innovative and already experimented methods when evaluating.
- Make sure that there are translation resources and if possible interpreters when working with diverse groups of C&YP within one group.
- In order to engage C&YP where there is a gatekeeper and maintain interest, it is important to use a 'light touch' initially i.e. using recording of the session rather than more intrusive methods of gathering evidence.
- Balance expectations about the platform.
- Run the dialogues over a period of time to build up trust.
- Use breakout groups so that everyone's voice can be heard.
- Using a hand-held wireless microphone can help to manage the conversations plus added benefit of recording them.
- Depth of conversations – as we narrow it down the conversations can be quite superficial.
- Share the observations and comments from others on the chosen topic so that the group can begin to have their own ideas rather than repeating current ones.

7 Conclusions

In relation to cycle 2 of the Social Dialogues phase, we have used the lessons learnt from cycle 1 to enable a cohesive and complete collection of results and later attainment of objectives. The

final and quality evaluation reports do note upon this and several instances of process iteration are visible on these fronts.

The positive outcomes achieved in the first year through the Social Dialogues continue to be relevant and have been further developed, providing a solid basis for further work as the project proceeds into its final year, and the consolidation of the WYRED approach to youth empowerment. These are listed here:

A new methodological approach for working with children and young people, centred on developing their agency and their voice. As the year has proceeded the approach has been refined and several partners have received very positive feedback from gatekeepers such as university professors and school teachers.

A substantial number of children and young people, across seven European countries, and a wide range of ages and socio-economic backgrounds, have been given an opportunity to share their views and explore their understandings of issues that concern them. Increasingly there is evidence of common ground.

The consortium has further developed its understanding of appropriate and ethical ways to network with and engage children and young people in social dialogue both online and off, which is evolving into a collection of good practices.

The project has developed a platform that functions as a safe space for children and young people to carry out their explorations and exchanges, which also serves to connect children and young people from different countries and environments, and acts as a repository for their work.

To reach a good level of congruence among data collected by each partner, in the new deliverables the partners have worked in particular on the data and results of the second cycle, so to provide a global and coordinated vision of this phase of the project and to facilitate the subsequent evaluation phase. For D53 further work needs to be completed in relation to a global and co-ordinated vision of the Social Dialogues. In Cycle 2 each partner had at least one topic as part of the social dialogues that related to the Delphi themes and online world. This has been a positive improvement from Cycle 1 where many of the themes discussed by the C&YP did not relate to the online world and hence made it difficult to have a co-ordinated vision and have meaningful evaluation. This work needs to be more streamlined and focused for Cycle 3 so that all Social Dialogues in some way relate to the Delphi/WYRED Themes. In relation to WP5

Deliverable D54 Key research questions, a global list has been collated under the 15 Delphi Themes - see deliverable report D54.

8 Appendices

8.1 WP5 Updated Social Dialogues Report Template

<https://repositorio.grial.eu/handle/grial/1884>

8.2 WP5 Corpus of Session Reports by Partner

<https://repositorio.grial.eu/handle/grial/1885>

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